

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPEECH BY USING INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract. Teaching and learning English have always been significant due mainly to the role and opportunities this language holds in today's world. And the actual value of the knowledge of the language is measured by the speaker's ability to use the language in communication. This research paper aims to discuss and look through possible means to enhance learners' speech at a young age and provide relevant examples.

Key words: communicative competence, speech, speech culture, communication.

Introduction. Teaching foreign languages at school should be aimed at developing and improving foreign language communicative competence, expanding and systematizing knowledge about the language, increasing linguistic horizons and vocabulary, and further mastering the general speech culture. At the present stage, teaching foreign languages is to form foreign language communicative competence.

One of the first domestic researchers who substantiated the concept of "competence" was A. In Khutorskaya. In his understanding, "competence" was "a set of interrelated qualities of a person (knowledge, skills, habits, methods of activity) set about a certain range of objects and processes and necessary for high-quality, productive activity about them" [five].

In the sphere of lingua didactics, the term "communicative competence" was introduced by M. N. Vatutnev, who understood it "as the choice and implementation of speech behavior programs depending on a person's ability to navigate in a particular communication environment; the ability to classify situations depending on the topic, tasks, communicative attitudes that students have before the conversation, as well as during conversations in the process of mutual adaptation" [1, p. 38].

Such foreign and domestic researchers carried out the development of theoretical and practical issues of foreign language communicative competence as I. L. Bim, M. Z. Biboletova, Jan Van Ek, I. A. Zimnyaya, N. D. Galskova, M. K. Kabardov, V. N. Kartashova, E. I. Passov, R. P. Milrud, S. Savignon, M. Finocchiaro, V. V. Safonova, E. N. Solovova, A. V. Shchepilova, and others. Foreign scientists have defined the concept of "foreign language communicative competence" as the ability of a person to understand and reproduce a foreign language correctly and by the sociolinguistic situation of real life [6], as well as functional language proficiency, interpretation, and negotiation of meanings covering communication between persons belonging to one or another speech community, or between one person and a written or oral text [7].

Researchers (I. L. Bim, R. P. Milrud, V. V. Safonova, E. N. Solovova, and others) believe that language communicative competence is the ability to communicate in a foreign language in various situations fully. Studies by E. V. Ertsishevskaya, M. K. Kabardov, R. P. Milrud, and V. V. Safonova state that foreign language communicative competence is a multi-component phenomenon. The traditional primary general education in a foreign language and speech, sociocultural, compensatory, and educational and cognitive competencies separate language competence. Language competence is understood as the mastery of new language means (phonetic, spelling, lexical, grammatical) by the topics, areas, and situations of communication selected for the primary schools, as well as the development of knowledge about the linguistic phenomena of the language being studied, different ways of expressing thoughts in native and target languages.

The term "language competence" initially arose in linguistics; it was first introduced to the science by well-known American linguist N. Chomsky. Gradually, the period penetrates the theory

and methodology of teaching foreign languages supplemented and expanded. Scientists of the Council of Europe distinguish the components of language (linguistic) competence: lexical, grammatical, semantic, phonological, orthographic, and orthoepic competencies. [4].

Methods and research material. Lexical competence is understood as knowledge of the vocabulary of the language, including verbal and grammatical elements, and the ability to use them in speech. Grammar competence is understood as knowledge of the grammatical aspects of the language and the ability to use them in speech. Grammar competence includes understanding and expressing specific meanings and arranging them in phrases and sentences.

The student's semantic competence lies in the knowledge of possible ways of expressing a specific meaning and in the ability to use them in speech. This is the assimilation of the word's lexical, grammatical, and pragmatic semantics. The basis of phonological competence is the knowledge and ability to perceive and reproduce speeches in foreign languages. Spelling competence involves knowledge of the symbols used in creating written language text and the ability to recognize and depict them in writing.

Orthoepic competence is correctly reading a word according to its graphic form [p. 110-117]. In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, there are various concepts of the content of the language competencies. However, according to domestic and foreign researchers, general sub-competencies phonetic, lexical, and grammatical competencies are considered part of linguistic competence. Forming and developing the lessons in a foreign language at school is necessary. The effectiveness of the formation and development of language competence largely depends on technology and means of teaching foreign languages. The use of interactive teaching aids contributes to the optimization of the educational process and the transition to a qualitatively new level of development and has several advantages over traditional forms of conducting lessons: students take an active part in the conduct of the lesson, activate knowledge, and display various personal qualities. The lesson should be organized, so that every student becomes involved in the learning process. Everyone makes a unique contribution exchange of knowledge, ideas, opinions, and methods of activity in an atmosphere of goodwill and interest, which allows children to gain new understanding, the teacher to effectively assimilate educational material, and acquire cooperation skills in a foreign language lesson.

Even though the authors of school teaching and methodological complexes in a foreign language offer various exercises for the development of language competence, in practice, every teacher tries to develop additional activities, tasks, game moments, and additional schemes to more easily explain a grammar rule or introduce new lexical units, and then and consolidate the knowledge gained.

Research and discussion. One solution to this problem is using information technology to create interactive exercises and tasks for developing all components of foreign language competence and, first of all, lexical competence because they are seen as a unity, and their formation is interdependent. The high level of development of the linguistic competence of schoolchildren is manifested in the fact that the student efficiently uses a large vocabulary both in direct and indirect communication, adequately using phraseological turns, proverbs, and sayings, typical for the speech of native speakers.

After analyzing new forms, means, and technologies for the formation of lexical competence, the possibility of using computer training programs, software for interactive whiteboards, Internet resources, Web 2.0 services and tools, and distance learning LMS Moodle platform, we concluded that one of the most effective and at the same time easy to use by teachers and students is the interactive Web 2.0 Quizlet service, which is gaining more and more popular among foreign language teachers around the world. [3, p. 295].

Generalization of the international experience of teachers (according to the data on the official website, every month, more than 20 million students from 130 countries work with more than 140 million learning modules on a wide variety of topics) using this resource to teach a variety of subjects, including

and a foreign language, namely foreign vocabulary, allowed us to conclude that there is no precise term for Quizlet. The site's creators refer to it as a "study tool" (learning tool).

In the review of this service, which is presented by the PC company (<http://www.pcmag.com>), there is a definition of "a platform for rote learning" (a platform for learning by heart), domestic authors use the purpose of "an online service for creating and using flash cards and educational games" [2]. In our research, we define Quizlet as a Web 2.0 service because this is the definition most commonly used in applying information technology in education.

One of the advantages of Quizlet, which attracts a large number of users, is the simplicity of its use. Also among the advantages are the following: 6 models (modes) of learning; choice of any foreign language for creating flashcards, audio accompaniment; voice recognition system; availability; free use cases; Compatible with IOS and Android Apps. Among the shortcomings, one can only single out that the system recognizes only answers that are entirely consistent with the task.

This service in the process of developing lexical competence can be used in four ways:

- demonstration: flash cards (Cards), which the teacher can create himself with exactly those lexical units that his students are studying at the moment; you can add a picture for better understanding and memorization; a big plus is that you can listen to the pronunciation of all words and record your voice, while you can vary the speed of the cards;
- consolidation: in the Learn exercises (you need to write a translation of words) and Speller (note the words you hear), the first operations with lexical units are performed, which allows you to memorize them consciously;
- control: Test tasks and games Scatter and Space Gravity. The test consists of charges for matching, multiple choice and true/false statements, written translation words;
- an interactive online game for the entire Quizlet Live class: during the game, not only is it fixed studied material, but it also develops interpersonal communication skills.

In addition, Quizlet allows teachers to create virtual classrooms and record their students in them, which facilitates the work of evaluating and commenting on students' work. So, in the Test module, after its execution, the teacher and all other group members see all the results in the section Scores. They are presented as a pedestal, which motivates them to achieve the status of "champion." Thus, studying the possibilities of Quizlet in teaching foreign language vocabulary, analyzing the experience of teachers already using this tool in their practice, as well as their understanding of using it in the course of teaching a foreign language, allowed us to determine that this tool can be used for the presentation and expression of the semantics of new vocabulary or for the formation of ideas about the sound and graphic image of a lexical unit, i.e., at the first stage of the construction of the linguistic competence of schoolchildren, which, in turn, is the basis of language competence. Language competence improves as lexical competence develops, i.e., their development is interdependent, and interactive learning tools, including Web 2.0 services, positively affect this process.

Conclusion. As we mentioned above, learning any foreign language, in our case, English, and teaching it requires separate individual attention from students' and teachers' sides. Enhancing students' communication competence is considered to be of utmost importance. All methods and techniques used during the lessons should provide an appropriate atmosphere and motivation for students to speak freely and correctly. We tried to offer possible strategies that assist students in improving their communication skills that revealed efficiency during classes.

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